

**A STUDY ON STUDENTS PARTICIPATION TOWARDS
HIGHER STUDIES WITH REFERENCE TO DHANALAKSHMI
SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS),
PERAMBALUR**

M. Manimaran*, Hari Kishore Varma & S. Vinoth****

* Assistant Professor, Department of MBA, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

** II Year Student, Department of Management Studies, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to assess the Students Participation towards Higher Studies with Reference to Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur.

Key Words: Willingness of Students, Awareness about Higher Studies, Awareness Program

Introduction:

A higher study is tertiary education leading to award of an academic degree. Higher studies, also called post-secondary education, third-level or tertiary education, is an optional final stage of formal learning that occurs after completion of secondary education. It represents levels 6, 7 and 8 of the 2011 version of the Education structure. Tertiary education at non degree level is sometimes referred to as further education or continuing education as distinct from higher studies Higher education, also called post- secondary education, third-level or tertiary education, is an optional final stage of formal learning that occurs after completion of secondary education. It is delivered at universities, academies, colleges, seminaries, conservatories, and institutes of Techniques and through certain college- level institutions, including vocational schools, trade schools, and other career colleges that award degrees. Tertiary education at non-degree level is sometimes referred to as further education or continuing education as distinct from higher education.

Literature Review:

Dr. Sonia Sharma Uppal & Dr. Karun Kant Uppal, (2019), this article is based on the failure of education reforms in India. In India there are more than one hundred and twenty five Crore people are living. After the independence there is a enormous growth of higher education take place in India. However, still in India there are utmost children who are uneducated. Government of India launched Sarv Siksha Abhiyan for all the poor family students, but such program also got unsuccessful. Failure of such program was done by the entire corrupt official. No doubt, Sarv Siksha Abhiyan is a pleasant program but the level of teacher to educate students is not up to the mark. If the teachers are not brilliant then what awareness they will give to the students.

According to Dr. Usha Tiwari, (2018), this article is based on the Organizational Climate in Higher Education Institutions of Madhya Pradesh. Organizational climate plays significant role for the growth of teachers' morale, confidence and motivation. When the climate of the organization is excellent then the teachers can make good relations with other teachers with higher job satisfaction. Poor organizational climate leads to increase the frustration, decrease in morale and decrease in job satisfaction in the teachers. All such things are the chief reasons for diluting the quality of higher education. If a teacher is not happy with their work, superior and subordinate relations then he or she cannot work properly. Educational institutes must start some training and development facilities for the teachers to flush out their stress level at job place.

According to Dr. Usha Tiwari, (2017), this article is based on Career Planning and Counseling of Teachers of Higher Education Institutions of Madhya Pradesh. Career planning is very imperative for the teachers of higher education. To provide value education, teachers have to improve their qualification, their knowledge and research activities to prolong in any educational organization. UGC must make compulsory the activities of career planning for every colleges and universities.

Narjes Safari, Hamid Reza Vaziranzjani and Zahra Akbari, 2016, this article is based on the Barrier of Entrepreneurship in Higher Education. In this article author want to say that there is an emergence need of higher education. Only a single person with creative thinking cannot run business organization effectively. To run any organization there must be a necessity of talented people which we can get it only by way of mounting the system of higher education. In all business organization people are functioning with their skills. Normally in each and every organization all the people are rewarded by their fixed monthly salary. But actually people must be rewarded by their performance.

According to Dr. Suhas A ad, 2012, this article is based on the Emerging Issues and Challenges in Higher Education. In this article author point out the variety of problems in higher education in respect to political interference, cast creed and religion problems and corruption etc. India is having more than 125 Cores of population. In India every year lakhs of people get higher education degrees, but the quality of higher education is not up to the mark. Day by day it is seen that the quality of higher education is declining because of various issues. In India after pass out from higher studies maximum number of students are not getting appropriate jobs in the market because of pitiable quality of education. Indian government spends lots of money on higher education but that money is not reached to all the educational institutes because of corruption.

Objective of the Study:

- A study on student’s participation towards higher studies with references to Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan College, Perambalur.
- To study the willingness of students to do higher studies.
- To know the awareness about higher studies to each student.

Research Methodology:

Research is the process of systematic and in depth study or search of any particular topic, subject or area of investigation, backed by collection, Compilation, Presentation and interpretation of relevant details or data. It is careful search or find out valuation facts, which would be useful for further application or utilization.

Research Design:

The researcher used Descriptive Research Design. Descriptive Research design means fact finding one. The Research used this research design to find out the fact of respondents attitude and opinion about student empowerment.

Sampling Design:

The Sampling type is Simple Random Sample which involves deliberating selection of particular units constituting a sample, which represents the universe, is used for conducting the study.

Sample Size:

Sample size denotes the number of sample selected for the study. They sample size for this study is fixed at 110 respondents.

Data Collection Method:

Data are the basic input to any decision making processing of data gives statistics of importance of study.

Sources of Data:

- Primary Data

Primary Data:

Primary Data were collected through Questionnaire. The data which are collected a fresh for the first time and happen to be original in character.

Statistical Tools and Techniques:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-Square Test
- Correlation

Limitations of the Study:

- The study on student’s participation higher studies to be completed within a specified period of time.
- Lack of adequate and or reliable information’s about the topic of the study.
- The survey is based on the option of the student, which may be biased.

Willing to do Higher Study for Career:

Option	Respondents	Percentage
Agree	48	43.6
Neutral	27	24.5
Disagree	35	31.82
Total	110	100

Inference:

The above table shows that 43.6% of the respondents are agree and 24.5% of the respondents are neutral and 31.8% of the respondent are disagree. The majority of respondents are agreeing.

Correlation Method:

Table Showing the Relationship between the Willing to do Higher Studies of Career

Willing to do study of career (X)	48	27	35	110
Willing to do a higher studies for getting job and future (Y)	59	33	18	110

Answer: $r_{xy} = 0.73$

Inference:

There is high positive correlation between willing to do higher studies(X) willing to do higher studies for getting better job and future(Y).

Suggestions:

- Give more awareness class about higher education
- Conduct motivation class for every students
- Suggest about the higher studies will help us know job position and designation
- Due to family background the students have thought doing their studies in abroad.
- Mostly each and every student has thought doing their higher studies in abroad.

Conclusion:

The progress of any nation depends on the quality of its education system. The quality of education depends on the quality management, quality teachers and quality students. Quality infrastructure is also a vital part of the quality institution.

The progress of any nation depends on the quality of its education system. The quality of education depends on the quality management, quality teachers and quality students. Quality infrastructure is also a vital part of the quality institution. Though the number of higher educational institution has been rising day by day, it is very disheartening to observe that the quality of education is not improved. It is also very disheartening to see that most of the youths who pass out from the colleges and universities are not competent enough to compete with the present day job market, which requires specialized skilled worker in every field.

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